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Abstract: Despite the fact that students receive news and are inclined to it, and despite the diversity of character, the teacher should teach students to think independently, observe, and draw conclusions.

Key words: pedagogues, technology, innovations.

Pedagogical technology is a systematic method of creation, application and determination of the entire process of teaching and knowledge acquisition, taking into account technical and personal resources and their interdependence, which set the task of increasing the effectiveness of educational forms. Effective use of pedagogical technologies, opening the way to modern knowledge in improving education, is one of the main requirements of today. The reform of the continuous education system in our independent Uzbekistan is aimed at establishing it on the basis of new state education standards. Currently, special attention is paid to the activity of the teacher and his pedagogical skills.

Recommendations for the application of the processes of pedagogical technology classes, which began in the pedagogical thinking of teachers working in the educational process, are very necessary for teachers. It is specially designed to increase students' activity on the basis of cooperation: students can listen, understand, respect other people's opinions, take into account other people's interests, teach them, influence them.

Understanding, perception, self-control, the ability to explain ideas clearly, clearly and in detail, the use of interactive teaching methods, self and others, "I" develops quickly and has a positive effect. By using interactive methods in teaching, a competitive environment was created between students, which allowed students to move forward, as a result, students began to learn together. Any interactive method will teach students to think independently when used correctly and purposefully. New pedagogical technology is a process that produces rational methods of the educational system in which the teacher is the main responsible person. Because its main task is to provide information to students in a quick, clear and understandable way.

Despite the fact that students receive news and are inclined to it, and despite the diversity of character, the teacher should teach students to think independently, observe, and draw conclusions. In this, the student is the main driving force, reading, reading, drawing, understanding the formulas of projections, being friendly with each other, and helping each other in solving the problems in front of them are their main tasks. The changes and updates taking place in the education system not only provide students with new knowledge, skills and qualifications, but also ensure that our young people are instilled in their minds and hearts with patriotic ideas in relation to society, the state, and nature. to himself and to other people.

The national training program defines a set of modern requirements for a teacher who prepares competitive personnel. The set of interrelated requirements describes the generalized model of the educator and based on it the following basic requirements: teaching skills, education skills. Personal qualities that provide the human factor in the educational process are the ability to objectively evaluate and control the knowledge of teachers.

This means that in order to fulfill complex, responsible and urgent tasks, as well as to form new views on the educational process, the teacher must have the following qualities:

Deep understanding of the nature of modern, scientific and cultural development;

Updating the system of knowledge about the world and man from a deep and broad perspective;

The use of information technology and training manuals in the teaching process, the ability to understand the Internet and use it to improve their knowledge.

- to know the methods of analyzing the effectiveness of pedagogical work and to be able to self-evaluate.

- to develop ideas about the problems of family education and upbringing.

Universal and national culture and values to understand the essence of national idea and national ideology economic reforms.

- to know the ways of effective use of pedagogical technologies in the educational process.

Creating conditions for students to think and exchange ideas with each other and create a friendly environment.

- Mastering the use of laboratory equipment and exercises to increase the effectiveness of the lesson.

- knowledge of technical tools and methods of using educational tools, such as teaching children through their own research, creativity, initiative and concrete actions.

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